

A Review of Moonlighting in the IT Sector And its Impact

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Abstract – *There is a rapid change in the global environment and the economy. As a result of remote work and inflation, some workers have begun moonlighting, working secondary jobs either to make ends meet or to earn a little extra spending money. In addition to taking on various dimensions, human resource management (HRM) practices are also changing. Recent years have seen an increase in the number of people holding multiple jobs. The prevalence of this phenomenon is attributed to flexible work hours and work-from-home options offered by most IT companies. During this time of economic change, employees are more concerned about their economic well-being than their professional advancement. In addition to their primary job, they have been doing extra work with other employers for extra pay. Employers' compliance policies are affected by moonlighting, as it affects employee work lives. A growing concern exists over the efficiency implications of moonlighting in the management of IT sectors. The study also compared the rate of moonlighting in the IT sector and the relationship between workers' main job and secondary job. Could the employee be working in two or more organizations without their current employer knowing? To prevent employees from moonlighting, how can organizations support them economically? How would it be if the employee handled all the tasks more effectively without hindering any of them? During the transition from blue moon to full moon, moonlighting practices by employees are of great concern.*

Keywords: Moonlighting, Part-time job, blue moon, Secondary-Job, Full moon, IT Sector, Quarter moonlighting, Half moonlighting, IT Market, side gig, Gig-Jobs, Freelancer, side hustle.

1.INTRODUCTION

In recent years, IT market flexibility has led to lower employee-employer loyalty, rising unemployment risk, and shorter job tenures. As an Outcome of these changes, individuals must seek alternative strategies to ensure employment security and a continuous and higher income stream. Occupational mobility has become more important in modern job markets because of rapid technological change and the requirement for continuous skill updating. The above volatility has forced a significant number of workers to develop an energetic strategy of holding multiple jobs or moonlighting to cope. In addition to addressing financial constraints, multiple jobs can ensure uninterrupted employment spells and provide an opportunity for further career advancement by accumulating occupation-specific expertise. As the Indian IT market has become more flexible, moonlighting has become an important characteristic. To supplement one's income, a person takes on a side job, or side hustle, or side gig, in addition to their primary job. Some side jobs are done because of necessity, such as when a person's income derived from their primary job is not enough to support them, or simply to earn more money. The practice of moonlighting refers to working a side job after normal working hours. It is possible to keep more than one-side job simultaneously, such as a full-time job, part-time contract, or freelance work. In India, side jobs are becoming increasingly

popular. With wage stagnation and low wage growth, income hasn't kept pace with the cost of living, leaving nearly a third of people with side jobs unable to make ends meet. Taking on side jobs is usually done in order to increase disposable income. It is typically referred to as a "day job" when an individual's primary job is only meant to provide income so that they can pursue a side job of their choice. For a deeper understanding of income growth and career progression, as well as for the purposes of developing future IT market policy, it is crucial to examine the relationship between occupational experience, moonlighting, and job/occupational mobility. Additionally, holding multiple jobs has a negative impact on employee health, productivity, work-life balance, and overall wellbeing. Increasingly innovative techniques are being developed to motivate employees to work more effectively. Worldwide, there is fierce competition for survival of the most qualified, and organizations must adapt to the changing work culture and adopt new human resource practices. People who refuse to change will remain in the backyard and face defeat. It is therefore imperative that the organization implement the latest human resource practices. For most of us, one job is enough. Some people, however, are barely able to pay their bills, so they take on another or even a third job just to survive. In what ways does moonlighting affect the workplace and employees? Moonlighting, or holding a second job in parallel with one's current job, is a frequent practice that ranges from blue moonlighting to full moonlighting. The transition from blue moon to full moon and its effect on organizations should be understood first.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this article, will examine various aspects of employee moonlighting. Data have been collected from the period of January 1, 2014, to Sep 18, 2022. In this study, secondary data are compiled from journals, articles, books, and the Internet.

2.1 Moonlighting: Why Do Employees Do It

There are many reasons why employees choose to take on a second job. The obvious reason is monetary consideration, but there are other reasons for employees to take on a second job as well. Following are some of the major reasons why people moonlight:

2.2 There are monetary reasons for this: As a reward for the effort an employee puts into the job, money is the major benefit. In Maslow's hierarchy of demands, money helps satisfy the first two levels, Needs related to physiological health, safety, and security. Employees can earn additional income by taking on a second job. A country like India, where the pay level is not so high, encourages employees to take on more than one job in order to meet their basic needs.

2.3 Experience in the Workplace: It is common for employees to want to gain more experience in their fields. It's especially important for new entrants who want maximum exposure in a limited amount of time. In a brief period of time, doing two jobs simultaneously allows them to gain the maximum amount of experience.

2.4 Skills Acquisition: New skills are learned by employees, which enhances their personal development. Their employability is further enhanced by the increased skill set.

2.5 Find out what career options are available: It is common for employees to be dissatisfied with their current career choices. It is possible that they would like to explore other career options without leaving their current position. Can discover new opportunities in different fields by taking on a second job simultaneously.

2.6 Security of employment: Employees are concerned about the stability of their jobs. Whenever an employee's first job becomes unavailable, they may accept another job to meet their basic needs.

2.7 The steps to starting a business: It is common for employees to want to start their own businesses. A business's initial stage requires investment, and returns come later, so they stay on the job and treat it as a shock absorber. Additionally, the job teaches them the skills needed to start a successful business. In this way, employees hone their skills on the job and use them as a shock absorber should their business venture fail.

3. THE SITUATION OF MOONLIGHTING IN INDIA

Recent research has shown, by this year, around 30% of India's work force will have to work remotely. Figures may change, as telecommuting is on the rise. Telecommuters, or those who quit their jobs to work remotely, can now double their wages thanks to a new trend. Multiple tasks simultaneously. Multitasking is highly recommended for Moonlighters. Working as an IT professional has not only doubled the salaries of employees but also provided us with valuable experience. It is worth noting that Moonlighters believed the employer's words. They kept their end of the deal if it did not conflict with their actions. It is not a secret! Many professionals now have two corporate IDs, two email addresses, and two bosses in WFH mode. Techies know this, especially in the US. The concept has also evolved into a community called Overwork, which helps professionals lead a double life. But India is a different story. This concept is old in America. To earn more money in the US, they may choose to work for two different employers on different shifts. Suppose the waiter works in both restaurants in the morning and in the evening. This allows a person to make more money with two jobs and pay the bills. Now we have entered the field of technology.

because everything works remotely, and results come out. Today's employees have more free time thanks to the telecommuting culture, so they can work more. There are companies that are honest about telecommuting and are open and transparent about the concept. That is why it works. However, this is not possible in the service sector. Even though it is a new trend, there has been a lateral shift in India. Examples include independent project consultants and mentoring teachers outside the school. A second example is people who have different jobs and are part-time LIC agents. Many successful startups were created when the founders made extra money. Moonlighters are good managers. It all depends on time management. Not everyone is freelance or moonlighting. Only 20% of professionals are smart enough to do this and can do more. Even so, Moonlight manages multiple projects simultaneously, offering professionals a number of benefits, such as learning new skills or retraining them. It affects them more. As a result, they will be at par with their competitors around the world. They also gain experience that helps them find good jobs. They make more money.

4. THE MOTIVATIONS WHICH LEAD TO MOONLIGHTING

Several probable causes have been identified in the research on secondary job motivations (SJ):

People may be confined by their primary job's hours or earnings; for example, they may be willing to work additional hours or take a higher-paying job but are not given the option to do so. Total earnings in the principal employment may be affected by laws regarding working hours, short-term working contracts during periods of low economic demand, or the absence of a minimum wage. This condition may worsen the individual's or his or her household's financial constraints, including paid workers who do not encounter time limits at work but whose wages fall short of their target income. This is also known as the financial motivation [1].

- Employees who are worried about losing their main job may take on a second job to protect themselves against the risk of losing their main job and to give themselves more options for staying in the job market.

- People who have bad financial surprises may choose to get a second job instead of saving money as a safety net.

- IT workers may choose to take on another job in order to learn new skills that will allow them to transition to a different field of work. SJ can assist people in making job changes or operate as an effective incubator for entrepreneurial activity, enhancing their prospects of changing careers. This idea emphasizes the investment side of moonlighting rather than the consuming side. It is related to the job diversity reason, but it varies in that it takes the money side of moonlighting into account.

- Secondary job satisfaction may differ from primary job satisfaction. Job heterogeneity may therefore be another motive for moonlighting.

According to the hours restrictions theory, there should be a negative link between employees' primary job earnings and their likelihood of taking on secondary occupations. The diverse job motive, on the other hand, recognizes that people may pick a side hustle for reasons unrelated to their first job's hours or compensation. The early literature on secondary job hours supported the hours-constraint motive, as it was established that the number of hours worked in second occupations was inversely connected to the number of hours worked and earnings in primary employment. Nonetheless, it becomes clear that not just the primary job's income level but also the extent of a wage boost is crucial for lowering the take-up of second occupations, particularly among the lower-paid. The boost in income brought about by the higher minimum wage may not have been sufficient to persuade low-income people to give up their second job [1].

Workers who take over a second job due to time restrictions in their primary job should have shorter moonlighting periods than those who take over a second job for non-financial, intrinsically rewarding reasons. Indeed, the standard theory based on hourly limits fails to account for the reality that workers can escape hurdles in their primary job by looking for a new one over time. This calls the temporal constraint argument as the sole explanation for SJ into doubt. There is no evidence to support the idea that workers may moonlight in order to protect themselves against job instability in their primary employment [2]. According to certain research, SJ is more common among public sector personnel and those with long-term contracts. This implies indirect connection between job security and moonlighting. People will consider adopting up another job if their primary work gives some level of stability. Thus, recent empirical study has concluded that money is not the only relevant element. Secondary employment motivations vary, but most typically involve appreciation of the non-financial components of the job. For many people, working numerous jobs is a personal approach for achieving or restoring job satisfaction through more difficult sorts of work or skill development [1].

5. MOONLIGHTING AS A BUSINESS

People who want to start their own business are often encouraged to keep up with their day job while starting a new business. As a business, Moonlighting minimizes the risks associated with starting a business from scratch. Startup projects usually don't pay off financially in the first few months, so working full-time can give your business a shot. Conflicts are common when an employee and employer start a new business while continuing to work for their current employer [7]. Employment contracts often contain clauses and restrictions that prohibit employees from performing additional work or claiming ownership of what they have created. These intensive projects can distract an employee from their primary task, which can jeopardize their loyalty and duty of care. That's why

moonlighters need to be careful when working in startups.

6. THE ETHICS OF MOONLIGHTING IN THE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY INDUSTRY

It is no secret that Indian workers face a double-edged sword when it comes to moonlighting. This can be a great way to earn extra income and gain valuable experience while working full-time for an organization, but if caught it can be considered a breach of contract and lead to termination. Moonlighting in the tech industry is a hot topic. Simply put, it's a scam [3]. An unstable work environment, fears of recession and job losses have sent the IT industry into a panic. As a result, moonlighting is clearly visible and becoming a haven for remote workers who want to secure an income channel in any way possible. Since January 2022, the startup has laid off more than 11,000 employees, and some tech companies are maintaining variable pay to ease pressure on tight margins. More remote workers managing two or three jobs simultaneously during the pandemic has sparked this trend in the IT industry. Although moonlighting is an attractive option for employees because it helps them achieve a career, growth and additional income, employers are concerned about company information and the risk that employees may not be able to give their all. It can be on the top and bottom of the pyramid. People at the top of the hierarchy typically augment their income through consultancy, while those at the bottom can find a few jobs in the gig economy. Moonlight receives an additional 10% of the employee's base income [4]. Recently, the Indian food ordering platform announced a non-disclosure policy that allows its employees to undertake external projects for free or at an affordable cost. This can be considered an after-hours or weekend activity that does not adversely affect the productivity of full-time employees and does not create a conflict of interest with the food delivery company's business. Implementing this

requires carefully crafted rules and regulations by the IT industry, considering both the specifics and guidelines for which employees can perform additional duties. Experts argue that if the organization is unable to openly authorize these projects, the contracts it operates could lead to litigation against the company's personnel [4,5]. For Moonlight, if the contract contains a single, non-competitive employment contract, this could be considered cheating, which is the case with most traditional employment contracts. But the employment contract is not fraudulent if it does not have this clause or doesn't say how to get out of it [5].

7. THE IMPACTS OF MOONLIGHTING ON HUMAN RESOURCES

The Moonlight Act is an act to cover the cost accrued by doing two things at once. Moonlighting occurs when a worker has a full-time 9-to-5 job as their primary source of income and works at another job for supplemental income. For example, someone who teaches a school during [8] the day and runs a tutoring center in the evening. Some organizations don't care about employees working overtime, while others don't allow it because it can affect performance. Many work part-time to earn extra income, but some work part-time to improve their skills in other areas. Some do it for fun. Fatigue is caused by moonlight for several reasons. Dissatisfaction with the salary appears in the organization. Employees feel that the employer has lost morale and that the company's profits are high. Human resource management has a negative impact on working with employees. In most cases, moonlighting has a negative effect on hiring managers [9,10].

7.1 Motives:

Moonlighting can be done for a variety of reasons, including.

1. An extra source of income
2. Enhancing their capabilities for different job profiles

3. Employers do not appreciate their employees.
4. Taking advantage of extra time

Generally, moonlighting can be classified into four categories:

7.2 Blue Moonlighting: It is not uncommon for management to respond positively to employees' demands during performance appraisals and increase wages and benefits. But some workers are not satisfied with these benefits, and they wish to work part-time for extra income, but their efforts may not be fruitful because they lack skills. The term "blue moonlighting" refers to this type of disappointment [9].

7.3 Quarter Moonlighting: Quarter moonlighting is when a worker seeks a part-time job for extra money after his primary job because he is unhappy with his salary. Quarter moonlighting may only help with meeting daily needs or increasing expenses [9].

7.4 Half Moonlighting: The majority of employees spend more than they earn. Luxury is important to them as well as saving money for the future. In order to get a sufficiently large additional amount, people spend 50 percent of their available time earning extra income [8]. This is referred to as "half-moonlighting."

7.5 Full Moonlighting: A situation in which employees in certain professions have extra time, or when they believe, their income does not compare to their expectations [8], or when buddies with lesser qualifications enjoy a higher status than them. As a result of hard times, these workers often start up their own business or industrial unit and continue to work their regular jobs. The second occupation, however, determines their financial and social standing. The term "full moonlighting" refers to this scenario [9,10].

8. THE EXPLOITATION OF FRESHERS IN THE INDIAN IT SECTORS WHICH LEADS TO MOONLIGHTING

IT was aware of this problem for years. It is widely known that recent graduates are exploited, causing problems such as turnover, undeclared employment and reluctance to return to work. The IT industry is making big profits in India amid a weak Indian rupee. In the Information Technology (IT) sector, sales increased by 13–14% due to rupee depreciation. IT companies are making high profits and senior employees are getting high salaries. Don't young people have to pay too? Over the past decade, the Information Technology (IT) industry has been hiring young workers[6]. IT companies in India pay huge salaries to their CEOs and other senior executives. In addition, junior staff will continue to receive the same salaries as in 2008–2009 in the form of compensation. Several major IT companies in India have recently cut salaries of some employees, including lower-level employees, due to higher margins. Sacrifice should be the duty of the elders. If the younger generation does not raise wages, how can the older generation get them? Do not treat them like little people but respect them equally. If these companies do not change their policies, they become mercenary organizations. In this industry, people come first, and employees are well looked after[6]. Ten years ago, the concept of seeing the bottom of a pyramid was widespread. Now that is almost never heard. It was the strength of the human spirit that made these companies successful. Human values were the basis of this field. Their deviance makes them a mercenary organization.

9. HOW MOONLIGHTING BENEFITS SMALL COMPANIES

The impact of Moonlighters on businesses, especially small ones, can be significant. This is an advantage for those who are Moonlighting. Small firms can greatly benefit from years of experience as they expand their growth. Moreover, this doesn't essentially mean sacrificing the productivity of busy work or sacrificing the employee's time outside of regular office hours. Due to budget constraints, companies looking for experts to build sales

processes were unable to hire people with many years of experience. Employees who earn extra income can offer hours of expertise that fit within their budget. Onboard consultants with CXO status and provide expertise under contract. Moonlighting is considered ethical and beneficial for small businesses. Today, these professionals are experienced, well-paid, and successful. Their aim is to share the knowledge with small companies and startups that are not in direct competition with them. The fact that these consultants may provide these services or guidance in their spare time does not interfere with their work. Thus, this concept is analogous to knowledge sharing [15]. However, according to experts, moonlighting should only be viewed positively if it does not interfere with people's main work and is very loyal to their current employer. Employees who do not perform their current duties properly cannot moonlight at the same time. It is unethical for a moonlighter to take a side job and undermine his craft.

10. MOONLIGHTING- THE IMPACT ON WORK-LIFE BALANCE

When deciding whether or not to let workers moonlight, it's important for decision-makers to think about how moonlighting affects employees' health and safety as well as their ability to balance work and life. Multiple occupations were linked to increased work- and non-work-related injuries. It is believed that this is the result of increased fatigue, an inadequate amount of sleep, or irregular work schedules and working conditions. Multiple occupations combined to increase psychosocial stress. In transition economies, moonlighting is common in the informal economy. As a result, if these activities are not carried out in the formal sector, the state is unable to improve social security systems and the quality of public services. Additionally, informal settings provide opportunities for individuals (especially health or education professionals) to misuse public money. These individuals frequently work within the public sector

as a secondary activity to private enterprise. Digitalization has also led to more online ways to make extra money, such as crowdsourcing and other paid and unpaid activities. The exact labor market conditions are not known such as waiting times, for workers in these unconventional organizations. Employers frequently violate minimum wage and hourly wage regulations, and employees who work for multiple companies frequently lack insurance rights.

11. HOW MOONLIGHTING SHOULD BE DEALT WITH

An employee can secretly hold two jobs for a number of reasons: moonlighting, overtime, and layoffs. By deliberately overcharging others, this employee tried to hedge his bet. However, sometimes this can conflict with the interests of the employer [12]. Many companies suffer because moonlighting leads to high turnover rates. Now the biggest challenge is to catch and identify the moonlighters. Businesses also promote a work culture based on distance and trust. Above all, business owners must understand that in unpredictable times, work ethics change, and the work environment is out of control. Or they should use new elements of this culture in the workplace. It also includes moonlighting. On the other hand, organizations need to improve their workplace culture [13]. To this end, policies or strategies can be introduced to create jobs that people want to work for. Happy employees don't waste time. Many companies also use tools to detect data breaches and monitor employee activity. Another way to overcome the dangers of moonlighting is to do this. For example, in the employment contracts of some companies there is a clause that prohibits an employee from engaging in honorary or other work, profession, occupation, or employment, either directly or through his agent, under any circumstances without prior approval. written permission from management. And also plan to conduct a series of assessments to identify red flags related to employee productivity and

engagement. Making sure that all employees are motivated and interested by using different evaluation forums and reward and recognition programs [14].

Organizations, on the other hand, cannot always manage their employees' behavior, let alone pass legislation prohibiting moonlighting. Employees frequently believe that if their employer does not like their job, then be it! They'll do it elsewhere. There is no method to keep them under control [11]. As a result, human resources develops more policies to bind their staff. Organizations can be selfish to some level, which creates a minefield. Yes, HR rules should establish rigorous guidelines for data leakage and the disclosure of any trade secrets. More importantly, because moonlighting is the new norm, there should be no rule or policy that makes it illegal. When there is such a scarcity of IT skills, it will only enhance production. It will benefit two companies rather than just one. Nonetheless, part-time workers suffer risks as well. In some situations, they may be sacked, and firms may launch legal proceedings against them. Burnout is also very likely to occur when an employee does two jobs at the same time. It is not unusual for them to be exhausted and stressed all of the time. As a result, they may make costly mistakes and have decreased productivity. Employers frequently don't object when employees turn their passions into well-paying side jobs or side hustles. If the situation worsens, the employer and employee may have a conflict of interest [13]. Because moonlighting or side hustles are now the norm, it is essential that employers be honest and forthright with employees who participate in them.

12. SUMMARY AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Secondary job (SJ): Hour or income restrictions can make additional income from a side job an important source of financial security for people with limited income or hours at their main job. Important human capital spillover effects also occur between primary and secondary

employment, resulting in a positive association between SJ and later career options. SJ provides individuals with a channel to learn new skills and expertise, which may then be used as a steppingstone to a new career path, including self-employment. People who choose a different occupation for their second job than for their main job are more likely to change jobs completely and have a different type of job in their subsequent main job. Those who live in low-income homes or who encounter unexpected economic shocks, on the other hand, are more likely to work several jobs. Even though SJ is likely a symptom of broader struggles for low-income IT workers to maintain a decent standard of living with a single job, having a second job may be linked to more physical and mental stress or exposure to unsafe or unofficial working conditions, especially in less developed economies. In general, policy intervention may not be needed; but, in circumstances where market failures may necessitate some action, policy interventions must be carefully tailored to account for the underlying motives and conditions of SJ. For example, when SJ work is done on the edge of the IT sector, the government should focus on stopping unreported work, protecting lower-threshold income levels, and making sure that health and safety rules are followed. Moreover, researchers are now acknowledging that people other than low-income workers conduct SJ[1]. Acknowledging and recognizing skills gained through part-time work can be an effective strategy for increasing job mobility, which is a key goal of employment and skills policy agendas. Also, SJ could be added to the policy tools that are used to encourage entrepreneurs in the IT job markets of today.

13. CONCLUSIONS

It's hard to come up with one set of regulations for disciplining employees who moonlight. The rules that bosses and workers must follow when they are working together can be different depending on the

situation, and there are lots of different reasons why someone might need to be disciplined at work. It doesn't seem necessary to conclude that any attempt to fit disloyalty cases into a unified theoretical framework is doomed to failure. Conceptual structure can be established for moonlighting cases so long as it is understood that specific provisions of a collective bargaining agreement must always be considered in evaluating the appropriateness of any discipline imposed for moonlighting. There are certain criteria to consider when deciding if moonlighting is allowed. If an employee accepts a job outside of their primary employer that interferes with their ability to perform their duties, they may be disciplined. The fact that there are times when the issue is unimportant does not mean that an employee cannot be fired if they are consistently late, frequently absent, or simply underperforming due to fatigue from their second job. Instead, an arbitrator ought to determine if the allegation is in fact accurate and whether the employer adhered to the pertinent provisions of any collective bargaining agreement when imposing discipline. It is not appropriate to prohibit employees from working for the competing business or restricting their outside financial activities to an excessive degree. A rule like this should protect an employer's rightful goals. A disciplinary action may be upheld if a reasonable rule was broken without showing that the employer was hurt. It is only when there is the appearance of impropriety that a public servant's private financial activity should be limited. Foreseeing all situations in which an employee may be disciplined for the ramifications of having a second job is difficult, if not impossible. In dealing with such problems, employers can achieve consistency by keeping in mind the basic principles supporting the criteria previously set forth, namely that they might protect themselves against economic harm, reputational harm, and dishonesty on the part of their employees. Also, any

punishment given to dual employees must take into account whether or not the rule or provision is being used to make the industry as a whole more uniform. By adhering to these rules, the privacy of an employee can be protected, as can the employer's legitimate interests. Furthermore, by preventing disengagement, acquiring new skills, and igniting passion, moonlighting may aid employers in maintaining competence and productivity. Employees may also suffer from burnout as a result of moonlighting. In addition, it may contradict the purpose of holidays, vacations, and time off. Aside from that, because of the pandemic, the workforce is bound to seek alternative ways of securing their livelihoods through paid microwork and mini gigs in case of sudden layoffs, so moonlighting through platform work during frequent lockdowns is seen by tech-savvy IT professionals as an economic safety cushion.

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